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Assessing and monitoring the development of systemic food loss and waste innovations using a systemic innovation readiness level assessment (SIRL) tool

Innovations often focus on a new technology with the TRL scaling as a very well known tool. Our aim is to broaden this by stimulating LLs to consider other relevant dimensions and establish a systemic readiness level scaling (SIRL).

The SIRL exercise is a 2-step process. The first step is to identify and describe all dimensions that are relevant for the innovation. The 5 generic dimensions to be addressed relate to technology, behavioural change processes, business operations and strategies, policy framework, and the value chain conditions and relations. It is crucial that all relevant dimensions are identified and described. For each, the LL describes what this dimension means and whether the current situation sufficiently enables the development and implementation of their innovation. As such, they are able to timely identify and address obstacles to reach systemic impact.

The second step is to improve the innovation architecture. LLs describe for each dimension (1) the current situation, (2) what level 9 would look like and (3) the different steps that are needed to grow their innovation from the current situation to the level they aim to achieve. Finally, these descriptions can be linked to the readiness level scales available in the literature and assign numbers to each step.

This exercise will show which dimensions are least developed; these are the bottleneck dimension(s) and require the LLs' focus. The SIRL exercise needs to be repeated at least 3 times during the project lifetime. After every SIRL round the bottleneck dimension could change, thus shifting the focus of the scaling up process. The end result is an innovation package with adequately developed dimensions; a systemic innovation that effectively reduces food loss and waste. ■